

IMPERIAL INTERVENTIONS AND CULTURAL DISRUPTION IN PASHTUN SOCIETY: A CRITICAL STUDY OF THE DOMESTICATION OF WOMEN IN PASHTO TAPA

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ABSTRACT

This study critically analyses the agency and social role of women in Pashtun society through two different periods of its history i.e before the USSR invasion and the USA proxy wars and in its aftermath. The study critically analyses the influence of the war on the Pashtun culture and society especially with reference to the women rights and agency. The study examines how women's rights and agency underwent drastic changes. The study contends that the existing status of women is not indigenous trait of the Pashtun culture rather the war and extremism resulted into women's domestication. The study uses the Pashto Tapa as the primary source of the data. The analysis is conducted under the theoretical framework of Jeffrey C. Alexander's Cultural Trauma and Collective Identity (2004). The study concludes that women's rights and agency has been affected by the external ideologies and the maneuverings of the interested sections.

Key Words: Pashtunwali, Culture, Patriarchy, Tapa, Women Agency and Afghan.

Introduction

Women's rights are a key part of human rights and social justice. They help guarantee equal access to opportunities, freedoms, and responsibilities. Throughout history, women have worked hard for recognition, equality, and full participation in all areas of life. At the World Conference on Human Rights, the United States Secretary of State stated that he considers the protection and promotion of women's human rights to be a "moral imperative" (Thomas, 1995, p. 219). Women's rights and agency vary from culture to culture; in some cultures, they are domesticated, confined to domestic activities, and deprived of social, economic, and even cultural rights, whereas others grant them agency and entitle them to full rights

alongside menfolk. Historically, Pashtunwali, the Pashtuns' way of life, also believe in full rights of women in all walks of life. But due to external interventions, such as neo-colonial and imperial tussles on Pashtun soil, this approach to culture has changed. The Pashtun territories, which gave women space and equal rights, turned out to be strict toward women. This change occurred during the proxy wars between the USSR and the USA in Afghanistan. The Pashtun belt, comprising northwest and southwest Pakistan and southern Afghanistan, has remained a battleground for imperial wars since the early 19th Century. First, the British divided the region through the Durand Line (an imaginary border) and further created a buffer zone (FATA) and a province (NWFP) as a

bulwark against Russian infiltration. Second, the USSR invaded the region in 1979 in a bid to gain control of the trade route that was thwarted by US-Pakistan nexus through the latter's proxy called Mujahideen. Finally, the US invaded the region in the post 9/11 context to eliminate the Al-Qaeda-Taliban sanctuaries that were set up as an after effect of the US-USSR war (Ashraf & Farooq, 2021, p. 18).

The US-backed Taliban, who finally came into power in Afghanistan, can be seen as an example: Girls and women are denied education, health, and employment outside the home; once again, under the requirement that they wear the burqa, they have become veiled ghosts deprived of even the most basic of human rights (Agosin, 2002, p.1). In the Pashtun areas of Pakistan and Afghanistan, war and extremism had a major impact on women's lives. Women who used to take part in cultural and economic activities, like singing at weddings, working in the fields, and running households, were silenced by fear, displacement, and violence. The US-led War on Terror in Afghanistan conducted for the aim of eliminating Al-Qaeda and Osama-bin-Laden has brought about enormous economic, social and political changes in the region (Ahmad, 2010, p. 102)

Folklore of any society reflects its culture, ways of life, tastes, and mores. Pashto folklore is no exception in this regard. Tapa, a central pillar of the Pashto folklore, carries and preserves the rich cultural practices of Pashtun society. Pashto folklore embodies Pashtun traditions, beliefs and culture (Khan & Nusrat, 2020, p. 62). Tapa has always been used on occasions, at cultural festivals, and for national or collective causes, such as weddings, agricultural practices, wars, and deaths. Through Pashto Tapa and other oral traditions, women have expressed their emotions, struggles, and hopes. Their poetry and stories reveal strength in the face of suffering and serve as a record of their continued fight for identity and respect within patriarchal and conflict-affected societies. Examining women's rights in this way is not only about identifying injustice but also about understanding women's power to preserve culture, drive change, and redefine their place in society. The instances of Tapa under study are formed

during activities that demonstrate women's political, economic, and social engagement. In addition to these collective spheres, Tapa is also used for the individual sphere, where a woman expresses her emotions as an individual.

Tapa is a significant Pashto folklore genre, enduring for centuries and reflecting diverse aspects and challenges of Pashtoon society. With regard to Pashto folk songs, Salma Shaheen, a Pashto scholar and poet, says, "We have 85% of the folklore created by women. This poetic folklore has been widely used in Pashtoon society. It has been mainly formulated by Pashtoon women, and they frequently use it on various occasions (Ahmad & Alam, 2023, p.338) This poetic folklore has been widely used in Pashtoon society. It has been mainly formulated by Pashtoon women, who frequently use it on various occasions (Ahmad & Alam, 2023, p. 338).

Pashto Tapa is a short but deeply emotional form of folk poetry and is one of the most important ways Pashtoon people express themselves. Through Tapa, Pashtoon women have shared their love, sadness, resistance, and hopes for freedom. These Tapa show not only their feelings but also their social status and the cultural expectations they face. The Tapa, a concise yet evocative form of Pashto folk poetry, has long enabled Pashtun women to voice love, longing, grief, and endurance (Israr & Bibi, 2025, p. 186). Tapa often reflect Pashtoon society, showing women's strength, patience, and the quiet struggles they go through. Researching Pashto Tapa deepens understanding of Pashtoon women's experiences and ideas. It illustrates how, despite societal restrictions, women have maintained a vibrant cultural presence and contributed to preserving Pashtoon identity through oral tradition and artistic expression.

The study analyses the reflection of women's agency and entitlement to rights through the Tapa, the proxy wars in the region, and in the aftermath.

Research Methodology

The methodology of the study is qualitative, based on the textual interpretation of selected samples of Tapa, with a special focus on relevant structures,

expressions, and words that reflect women's social and cultural roles in Pashtun society. The study has selected two periods: one before the imperial intervention, the war, and extremism, and the other after it. The selected samples are analyzed across different historical periods and compared with respect to women's rights, agency, and social and cultural roles. The analysis is conducted within the framework of Alexander's *Cultural Trauma and Collective Identity* (2004).

Theoretical Framework

Alexander (2004) argues that cultural trauma occurs when a group perceives an event as deeply changing its shared identity and social life. The trauma comes from how people interpret and give meaning to the event, not from the event itself. This process leaves "indelible marks upon their group consciousness" (p. 03) and changes how they remember the past and imagine the future. Alexander explains, "Cultural trauma occurs when members of a collectivity feel they have been subjected to a horrendous event that leaves indelible marks upon their group consciousness, marking their memories forever and changing their future identity in fundamental and irrevocable ways" (p. 09). This shows that trauma is created through shared meaning, storytelling, and the ways events are represented, rather than being a direct result of the event itself. Alexander's theory helps explain how ongoing conflict and extremism in Afghanistan have shaped Pashtun communities, turning long-term suffering into a common story about identity, loss, and social change. The theory also shows how political and social upheaval can change community norms, gender roles, and practices, as reflected in Pashto tapa.

The Social and Cultural Position of Pashtun Women before the Imperial Intervention

Before the 9/11 attacks, Pashtun women held respected roles in both their households and communities, with their active participation in farming, weaving, and livestock care vital to family survival. Their essential contributions gave them a position of influence, demonstrating that their lives extended beyond domestic spaces and

involved meaningful engagement in Pashtun society's cultural and economic fabric:

We were among hundreds of men but no one dared to disrespect any female, Some of the participants would smoke cigarette during the dance, and the women had no prescribed dress-codes such as the shuttlecock burqa...The women used to perform Attan with bare heads, or simply a Chaddar draped on the shoulders. (Kakar, 2021, p. 38).

Culturally, women were seen as the heart of Pashtun tradition. They took part in weddings, harvest festivals, and local gatherings, where singing, dancing, and reciting *Tapa* were expressions of emotion and joy. These *Tapa* often spoke of love, separation, longing, and pride, offering women a poetic outlet in a society where direct expression was often restricted. "that at evening men and women would meet unreservedly, join hands in circles, and together dance the intoxicating Attan" (kakar,2021, p.35). When a Pashtun felt suffocated in the restrictions of his family and wanted change, he turned to the dancing girls for fun and merry-making." Rarely were they viewed with respect, but the rulers of Swat provided them a space to demonstrate their skills and assured their security. (Buneri, 2011).

The Gudar was more than just a place where women collected water. It stood for freedom and sisterhood, offering a space where women could share stories, talk about personal matters, and support each other emotionally. Pashtun women played a vital role in preserving cultural traditions. They attended social gatherings, weddings, and festivals where singing, dancing, and reciting *Tapa* were central. These events allowed women to express emotion, creativity, and belonging.

They often met at community spots like Gudar to fetch water, share stories, and strengthen friendships. Through these daily interactions and cultural practices, Pashtun women didn't just preserve their heritage, they embodied it:

هغه ساعت به کله راشی
چي د اشنا سره به بر گودر له ځمه
(Khan, 2020, p.76).

Translation: When would the hour come to go to upper Gudar with my beloved.

This Tapa shows a woman's longing and hope to meet her beloved at the Gudar. The Gudar is not just a water source; it stands for love, freedom, and emotional connection. It also reminds of a time when women could move freely in public and share their feelings through poetry. The verse highlights the openness and honesty that were once part of Pashtun culture before the impacts of the of war and extremism.

که د زما د بدن پادیری
د گودر غاړه واخله منښه
(Daud, 1984, p.56).

Translation: If you miss seeing me rent a place near the water spring, my love.

In this Tapa, the Gudar is shown as a place where lovers can meet. The woman asks her beloved to stay near the spring so they can see each other, making an everyday place a symbol of affection and connection. Using simple and natural images, Pashtun women shared their deep feelings while staying within cultural expectations. The tone of the Tapa is bold yet gentle, showing how Tapa gave women a respected way to express love and longing.

اوبه د کوز گودر خوری دي
زه د جانان د پاره بر گودر ته ځمه
(Yousafzai, 2025, p.27).

Translation: The water from the lower spring is sweet. but I go to the upper spring for the sake of my beloved.

In this example, the woman chooses to go to a more distant and challenging Gudar for her beloved, showing her devotion and emotional strength. Fetching water serves as a metaphor for the journey of love, reflecting the effort and hardship involved in caring for someone. The Tapa also points to women's mobility and agency in the Pashtun society, where daily work was closely connected to emotional expression and community life.

سوله د خیره سره راغله
د ملا لور تپي کوي گودر ته ځینه

(Yousafzai, 2025, p.26).

Translation: Peace has returned with blessings the mullah's daughter goes to fetch water from the spring, singing softly

This Tapa stands as strong evidence of women's cultural freedom. For example, even the mullah's daughter, a figure often linked with modesty and religion, is shown singing as she goes to the Gudar. Through this verse, we see a society where music, poetry, and daily life flowed together naturally. Within that rhythm, women's voices were celebrated rather than silenced. These samples of Tapa reveal that the Gudar was much more than just a water source. It was a place where women shared love, joy, and their unique identities. Before 9/11, the Gudar stood for freedom, connection, and femininity in Pashtun life. At these springs, women's voices filled the air with poetry, affection, and the sounds of daily work. After 9/11, though, this tradition declined as fear, conflict, and new social rules limited open expressions of love and movement in Pashtun culture.

The following samples of Tapa show that Pashtun women played an active part in agriculture. The verses describe them working with men in the fields, harvesting crops, and doing other farming jobs that helped support their families and communities. This shows that women did more than just household work and were important to the economic life of Pashtun society.

باچائی تخت مے پکار نه دے
جانان به لو کړی زه به وړی ټولومه
(Daoud, 1984, p.75)

Translation: The king's throne means nothing to me. My beloved will harvest the land, and I will gather the crops

This Tapa shows a woman's pride in her hard work and her choice to avoid luxury. By saying the king's throne means nothing, she makes it clear that she values work and companionship more than comfort or status. Her willingness to work while hungry during the harvest shows both love and endurance. This also highlights how Pashtun women found dignity in their work and saw

themselves as equal partners with men in farming, not just limited to the home.

چی لو کوے گوئے به پری کری
پلار ته د وایه چی لوگری و اچوینه
(Daoud,1984, p.75)

Translation: When you harvest the field, your fingers might get hurt. Tell your father to send a plowman to help

This Tapa shows the hardships women faced while working in agriculture. The mention of sore fingers from plowing highlights the physical pain they went through in the fields. It also points to their important role in daily farm work, as they often took on jobs usually done by men. This Tapa's tone is both caring and realistic, showing the heavy responsibilities and struggles that shaped women's economic roles in Pashtun rural life.

دیسرلی لوونه گد شو
جینی په سرو منگلو وری تولوینه
(Daoud, 1984, p.75).

Translation: The spring harvest has begun. Girls with red bangles are gathering the crops
This Tapa highlights the link between femininity and labor. The image of "girls with red bangles" suggests that women kept their cultural identity and embraced their womanhood, even as they worked in the fields. Agricultural work was not seen as degrading but as a shared celebration connected to the seasons. When women joined the harvest, it represented unity, productivity, and the balance between beauty and hard work.

بارانه ورو رو پری وریزه
وری وری جینکی غر ته تلی دینه
(Khan & Nusrat,2020, p.72).

Translation: O Rain, fall softly. The young girls have gone to the mountains.

This Tapa focuses on women's work outdoors and their close relationship with nature. The speaker asks for gentle rain, showing concern for the young girls who have gone to the mountains, probably to collect wood or look after animals. The verse shows women's ability to move, adapt, and stay

connected to the land. It presents them as important members of the rural economy who face weather and hard work with steady strength. Taken together, these Tapa show that Pashtun women played active roles in their culture. They worked as farmers, gatherers, and caretakers of the land. Through their songs, they celebrated their strength, endurance, and the close connection they felt to both their work and their families. These verses keep alive the memory of women's independence and labor, which is very different from the restrictions they faced in aftermath of the war and extremism in the Pashtun belt.

Pashtun women were not only symbols of Pashtun culture, but they also actively participated in battles alongside men. The following examples show the involvement of Pashtun women with their male counterparts:

که د بچو سره تیاہ شمه
د وطن جنگ دے جنگ به ولی نه کومه
(Daoud, 1984, p.93).

Translation: Even if I am destroyed along with my children, this war is for my homeland, why should I not fight?

This sample shows a woman saying that her love for her country is stronger than her worries about her own safety or her family's security. She refuses to accept that a woman's only duty is to care for her home and children, and instead claims her right to stand up and fight for her country. The Tapa makes it clear that women feel just as much patriotism as men and are just as ready to face danger and make sacrifices for their homeland.

که په میوند کینی شهید نه شوی
گرانه لایه بی ننگی له دی ساتینه
(Ahmad, 2025, p.338).

Translation: If you are not martyred in the battle of Maiwand, my beloved, you will live a life of shame.

This Tapa, inspired by the historically significant Battle of Maiwand, a celebrated event in regional memory, depicts a woman urging her beloved to fight bravely and choose death with honor over a life of disgrace. Her voice reinforces martial values and challenges men to act with courage. She is not

a passive observer but an active moral force shaping the spirit of the battlefield. The Tapa portrays women as guardians of cultural honor who give moral legitimacy to men's participation in war.

ته په غزا کښی خان شهید کره
زه به خپل شمال ستا په زیارت وغورومه
(Ahmad, 2025, p.338)

Translation: Go and become a martyr in the holy war and I will spread my shawl over your grave
Here, a woman encourages martyrdom and vows to honor the fallen. She does so through a public act of mourning and reverence, spreading her shawl in tribute. Her willingness to tend to the dead and take pride in commemorative rituals places her at the emotional and social core of wartime sacrifice. She supports the fighter's cause and claims her place in the aftermath. She shares in both the commitment to battle and the duty of remembrance:

جندی می سری په قبر کښیری
په شهادت د خپل وطن جنت له ځمه
(Ahmad, 2025, p.338)

Translation: Place my red flag on my grave for through my martyrdom for my country, I will enter paradise.

This Tapa presents a woman as a martyr in her own right. She asks for the red flag, a symbol of battle, to mark her grave and claims spiritual honor for giving her life for her homeland. By doing this, the poem removes the distinction between male and female roles in war, making valor, sacrifice, and honor qualities they share. It shows that women, too, can act heroically, take part in public life, and show selfless devotion, fully joining in the ideals of courage and dedication that were once seen as only for men.

The samples of the Tapa show that Pashtun women took an active part in the moral, emotional, and symbolic sides of warfare. They urged men to fight, valued sacrifice, performed remembrance rituals, and sometimes imagined their own roles and martyrdom. In these verses, women are shown not as passive observers but as equal partners in the wartime ethic. They help

shape reasons for battle, share risks, and claim the same right to honor and remembrance. These voices clearly show that women's role in Pashtun warfare was real, respected, and celebrated in Tapa.

Imperial Interventions, Wars, Extremism and the Status of Women

In the post war scenario the social and cultural status of Pashtun women changed in many ways. Earlier the Pashtun society was traditional but still it gave women an active and respected role in daily life. Women worked alongside men in the fields, sang Tapa while collecting water from the Gudar spring, took part in wedding celebrations, and gave moral and emotional support during times of war. Their poetry, songs, and hard work were part of everyday rural life. However, after the war, displacement, and fear changed this world and silenced many of the ways women once expressed their freedom. After the incident of 9/11 the dynamics of Pashtun society became more religious ones towards women. Many young women, mostly from the lower middle classes, took their space in religion by wearing and by carrying more religious outlook, rather than losing their spaces at all (Rahim, 2021, p.26).

When conflict and ideological struggles took hold in the Pashtun belt of Pakistan and Afghanistan, daily life changed quickly. Extremist groups arrived, bringing violence and a sense of insecurity that forced women out of public spaces. Taliban banned the music and "the familiar beat of Attan Dhol is hardly heard in public" (Nawaz & Ali, 2016, p. 36). Activities that men and women once shared became divided by gender. Women who used to gather at Gudar to sing and collect water now stayed inside. Weddings became quiet, folk songs disappeared, and tension replaced joy. "There was a time when we used to dance together that were held regularly in Waziristan." She says that "we were participating it among the male members but hardly anyone dared to humiliate and disrespect us (Khan et al., 2019, p. 79).

Religious interpretations further increase gender in equalities in the country. 17.4 percent of those who think that women should not work outside the home base this on their belief that it would be

against Islamic Law (Alipour et al., 2022, p.42). The Tapa, which had been central to women's emotions and social life, faded away. Before Afghan wars, the Tapa was more than just poetry. It was a way for women to connect with their world. In these short verses, they shared feelings of love, longing, pride, and sorrow, linking their emotions to nature and their community. When extremist ideas spread, people started to see women's voices as a threat to religious and cultural traditions. Singing in public or joining social gatherings was criticized and sometimes even punished. On March 14, 2010, Afsana, a young female dancer from Swat, was killed by armed men in the Damaan Hindko area on the outskirts of Peshawar, the capital of Khyber-Pakhtunkhwa Province, 100 miles from Mingora. Afsana and her entire family had already fled the Taliban to the city. She, along with her sister Sana, had begun performing at weddings to earn a living for their displaced family. They were on route home from a party when they were attacked (Buneri, 2011). The Gudar, once filled with laughter and music, grew quiet. Its silence came to represent everything that was lost. This transformation is best described as the domestication of women. 36.6 percent of Afghan men prefer women to wear a burka, compared to 27.6 percent of women (Albrecht et al., 2022, p.57).

Domestication meant much more than simply staying at home. It led to a loss of movement, independence, and voice. Women were restricted not just to their homes, but also to narrow ideas of duty and morality. Their roles became limited to household work, separating them from the economic, social, and artistic life that had long shaped Pashtun identity. The fields, markets, and gathering places that once rang with their laughter and activity became quiet. Shopkeepers at Cheena Bazaar, a leading women's shopping center in Mingora, found themselves the targets of threatening letters for selling cosmetics, perfumes, and women's under-garments (Buneri, 2011). Even the tone of Tapa changed. Songs that once showed pride and playfulness began to express grief and loneliness. Before the wars, Pashtun women were vital to the economy. They worked in the fields, cared for animals, and supported their

families through hard work. Their efforts were often honored in poetry, blending love and labor. When conflict reached their villages, farming suffered, families left, and women's work faded from sight. Open fields became refugee camps and ruined homes. Survival replaced celebration. The voices of women in poetry and song were lost to the noise of war.

Women's roles in the moral and emotional life of warfare changed as well. In earlier Tapa, they encouraged men to be brave or mourned their losses with dignity. After 9/11, years of violence and fear made open expression difficult. The bold tone of older Tapa shifted to mourning and displacement. Women were no longer the fearless singers of courage; instead, they became silent witnesses to suffering. The Tapa, once a sign of resilience, began to reflect despair. When women disappeared from Gudar, the fields, and communal life, it reflected a bigger cultural loss. Their songs, laughter, and shared work were central to Pashtun community life. Silencing them upset that balance and left a gap in the community's identity. A culture that once encouraged participation and emotional expression became more focused on fear and control. This loss was both social and poetic, as the fading of Tapa also meant the fading of the people's voice.

Since Tapa were shared by women, silencing them broke an old oral tradition. As conflict and displacement affected families, younger people stopped learning or reciting these verses. The genre, once full of women's wisdom and emotion, started to fade. This decline shows both the limits placed on women and the loss of Pashtun cultural heritage. Attan is the local dance of the tribal areas in which men and women dance, singing songs on the beats of drums or Dhol. Even in the Hujras and guesthouses, there used to be a music program, followed by local dance or Attan. "It started vanishing during Afghan war and particularly due to the emergence of Talibanization in the aftermath of the 9/11 incident (Khan, et al., 2016, p.79). After 9/11, life changed dramatically for Pashtun women. Women who once sang at weddings, worked in the fields, and recited love poems while drawing water

now live behind walls that restrict their movement and expression. Their songs have fallen silent. Where they were once at the heart of daily and cultural life, their presence has faded. This shift from freedom to confinement, and from public voice to private silence, is one of the most significant social changes since 9/11. With the loss of women's songs, Pashtun society lost an important part of its memory, poetry, and spirit. After 9/11, Tapa's tone and themes changed. The lively verses that once celebrated love, work, and courage began to echo fear, loss, and constraint. War and violence seeped into everyday life, reshaping traditions and silencing once-active female voices. Women who had freely expressed their emotions through Tapa became quiet witnesses to pain and uncertainty. The effects of 9/11 may be divided into two parts: in the first part the poets have directly portrayed the situations and events which came into being due to Osama bin Laden, Taliban, and America. The second part has the work and poetry of those poets who have not mentioned the event directly but have analyzed the violation of human rights, havoc, uncertainty, terrorism and human's inhumanity and cruelty (Khalil, 2012, p.49). The war and extremism deeply changed Pashtun culture. They follow how war, fear, and social unrest changed daily life and took away traditions that once gave women respect and visibility in their communities. Pashtun women who used to work in the fields, sing at, and join public celebrations were now kept inside their homes. These verses together reveal how conflict changed freedom into silence and made women's participation disappear.

ملا دی خپلا ملايي کړی
ماله دی واحلی تمبلگه چی بی وهمه

Translation: Let the mullah (cleric) do his own religious duty; and I shall beat my own drum (Ahmad, 2025, p.343).

This Tapa supports a woman's right to express herself through music, celebration, and joy, even when faced with religious extremism. Before 9/11, women freely sang, danced, and played instruments as part of their communities. After 9/11, stricter Militant religiosity and conservative

rules took away much of that freedom. Women were discouraged or even banned from taking part in music and celebrations in public. The line now serves as both a memory of a more open time and a subtle act of resistance against rules that forced women into silence and isolation.

گودر ته خي الله دی مل شه
دی الوتکی پرون دری وژلی وونه

Translation: May God protect you on the way to Gudar .The drone hovering up has just killed three yesterday (Ashraf & Farooq, 2022, p.23).

This Tapa highlights the sharp difference between a simple errand, like going to Gudar, and the danger brought by modern warfare and drone strikes. Gudar, once a lively place where women gathered, became unsafe. Even small daily routines started with prayers for safety. The verse shows that women stopped going there because fear took the place of friendship. As a result, the social and cultural life that Gudar once offered faded away, and people stayed inside to stay safe.

زمونر دکلی نجونه مري دی
یا وخت خراب دي چی گودر له نه راځينه
(Shad, 2017, p.19).

Translation: The girls of our village are like the dead, it is such a bad time that they no longer go to Gudar.

The line "the girls of our village are like the dead" is deeply symbolic. It shows how women's voices and presence faded from Pashtun society. Being kept inside was like losing their cultural and emotional freedom. The once joyful gatherings at Gudar became silent, and the Tapa remained as the only way for women to express themselves, serving as a powerful reminder of what was lost.

بیا به منگی ته گوتی نه کرم
مور د گودر د تلو نه ما منعه کوينه
(Shzad,2017, p.4).

Translation: I will never touch the water pot again, my mother has forbidden me from going to the spring

This Tapa reflects the fear and confinement that reshaped Pashtun women's lives after 9/11. Before the conflict, Gudar was a vibrant meeting place. Women fetched water, sang Tapa, and shared their emotions freely. As war and insecurity spread, even routine activities became dangerous.

بانه دي مړه دي بنسکته گوري
لکه چی مور دي نوره کورکی بندوبنه
(Shad, 2017, p.3).

Translation: Your brows hang down lifelessly, looking down, as if your mother has already shut you inside the house

This Tapa uses drooping eyebrows to express sadness, shame, and loss of spirit. It's links the downcast look to a mother's command that her daughter stay inside. The girl's face becomes a sign of confinement, her freedom replaced by passivity.

From Social and Cultural roles to Women's Domestication and Seclusion

Comparing Pashtun society before and after 9/11 shows major changes in women's roles, visibility, and independence. Before 9/11, Pashtun women played key roles at home and in public. They worked with men in the fields, gathered at Gudar to fetch water and sing Tapa, and celebrated their culture through dance, poetry, and music. These daily activities showed their confidence, freedom to move, and social inclusion, highlighting how important women were to the community's economic and emotional life. After the war extremist beliefs and increased militarization changed daily life and disrupted these social structures. Strict rules, like enforcing the shuttlecock burqa and rigid religious codes, kept women at home and made them disappear from fields, markets, and community events. The Gudar, which used to be filled with laughter, music, and social gatherings, turned into a place defined by emptiness and fear. This change reached into moral and political life, not just social and economic areas. Before the war, women were seen as caretakers and also as moral leaders. Through Tapa and oral traditions, they encouraged men to be brave, honored martyrs, and showed unity. Their involvement showed that they were equal partners in the fight for freedom.

After 9/11, though, militant extremism worked to silence them. The women who once inspired resistance lost their voices as strict religious views took away their agency and place in public life. The shift from the fields to the home, and from Gudar to the battlefield, shows a move from participation to prohibition, from expression to silence. This forced domestication, kept in place by fear, ideology, and violence, not only limited women's freedom but also weakened an important part of Pashtun cultural identity. The Tapa, which was once a song of love, work, and courage, became a mourn for voices that were silenced.

Before 9/11, Pashtun women were central to agriculture and livestock management. They helped with plowing, harvesting, and caring for animals, which supported both their families and communities. Women were seen as equal partners in this work, not just helpers. Their presence in the fields showed independence and trust between men and women. As one Tapa says, "The king's throne means nothing to me. My beloved will plow the land, and I will gather the crops." This line shows pride in hard work and a preference for contribution and resilience over comfort. Agricultural work was seen as honorable, showing endurance, love, and commitment to family and homeland. Women's work in agriculture strengthened their role in society. By taking part in farming every day, they connected with others in the community, which helped them feel included and confident. In rural areas, their work was essential for survival and influenced daily life in Pashtun communities.

After 9/11, this partnership broke down. Militancy increased, and extremist religious ideas changed social norms and gender roles. Many farming areas turned into militarized zones, and public spaces that men and women once shared were now considered off-limits to women. Fears of drone strikes, militant attacks, and social criticism made it harder for women to move freely. Because of new religious rules, many families stopped women from working in agriculture. The arrival of the shuttlecock burqa marked a major change. Before 9/11, women's clothing showed modesty but did not fully restrict them. As Kakar (2021) explains, women often danced the Attan "with

bare heads, or simply a chaddar draped on the shoulders.” After the conflict, militant groups changed the idea of modesty to mean seclusion. The burqa became a sign of confinement instead of faith, taking away individuality and freedom of movement. Women who once worked alongside men in the fields became invisible at home. What was once a partnership based on shared work and trust turned into separation, enforced by fear and constant watch.

In the Pashtun culture Gudar, the village spring, was more than just a source of water. It was a social and emotional hub for Pashtun women, where they came together to fetch water, sing Tapa, and share stories. Gudar represented sisterhood, connection, and a shared identity. In this communal space, women could freely express their feelings through song, laughter, and poetry. At Gudar, daily routines went beyond just household chores and helped keep cultural traditions alive. The Tapa sung there showed love, but they also reflected the community’s identity and strength. For women, singing Tapa was a way to express themselves in a society where they could not always speak openly. In this way, Gudar stood for both moving freely and having emotional independence. After 9/11, this freedom was lost. The spring, once full of life, grew quiet. The verse “My mother has forbidden me from going to the spring” shows this change in a powerful way. A place that once meant openness and community was now off-limits. Women staying inside “four walls” showed not just physical separation, but also a sense of being held back. The fear behind this change was based on real threats. Drone strikes, militant patrols, and strict moral rules made public spaces unsafe. To protect their loved ones, families kept women out of community life. But this choice had serious consequences, cutting women off from social interaction, artistic expression, and a sense of belonging.

This confinement was part of a larger cultural decline. Where women’s laughter once filled the valleys, now there was only silence. The emptiness of Gudar became a symbol of how women’s public voices disappeared, showing how extremism replaced joy with fear and community with isolation.

Conclusion

In the Pashtun culture women played an important moral role during times of conflict. Through Tapa and oral traditions, they encouraged men to be brave, gave emotional support, and sometimes saw themselves as part of the struggle. Their words showed patriotism, sacrifice, and moral strength. One woman’s Tapa says, “Even if I am destroyed along with my children, this war is for my homeland, why should I not fight?” This verse shows defiance and a sense of shared responsibility, not submission. Women played an equal moral role in the shared fight for freedom. They honored men’s courage, grieved for those lost, and led remembrance rituals. Their influence reached beyond the home, shaping the community’s emotional and ethical life. The Tapa gave women a way to connect personal feelings with public duty, linking private sorrow to the group’s identity. However, after the intervention of the international powers in the Afghanistan and other belts of Pakistan, these voices fell silent. Extremist ideologies began to enforce strict religious interpretations that kept women out of public and moral discussions. Women were told to stay quiet, cover themselves, and withdraw from community life. Those who once encouraged men to be brave were now kept at home, no longer seen or heard.

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